

MEDICAL SCIENCES

IN LOW-PRESSURE GLAUCOMA, IS THE OPTIC NERVE PUSHED OR PULLED?

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Abstract

The first cause of irreversible blindness in the world is glaucoma or glaucomatous optic neuropathy (GON). Glaucoma (green disease) has been known since the Greeks, and to date it is a disease that is not understood, and therefore cannot be stopped or even less cured, although it has been extensively studied but poorly understood.

Primary Glaucoma of open angle (POAG), or Glaucomatous Optic Neuropathy (GON) is considered as a group of different pathologies that lead to characteristic damage to the optic nerve that leads to vision loss. A portion of these patients evolve with increased intraocular pressure (IOP), but the majority present with normal intraocular pressure levels.

And the increase in IOP is the only risk factor that is currently managed in medical practice, either by pharmacological or by surgical means. But despite the efforts of researchers, ophthalmologists, and patients, POAG or GON continues to be an important cause of vision loss in the world.

Although some technical problems are arguing, for example, to measuring intraocular pressure, since there is no known optimal method that works ideally for all patients, studies also citing the variable thickness of the cornea, which varies from patient to patient, it even varies in the same patient throughout the day. Furthermore, normal values of intraocular pressure are not conclusively determined.

The above is to give an idea of the complexities surrounding this epidemiologically very important disease.

In this article, we will refer to a fundamental anatomical feature of glaucoma and that is the characteristic excavation of the optic nerve (bean pot excavation) which is supposedly due to the increase in intraocular pressure pushing the inside of the eye, and since hypothetically, the optic disc is the weakest part of the eyeball, it gives way and the tissues that make it up give way to the increase in pressure, and eventually they become deformed, progressively adopting the appearance of a pot of beans.

But there is another possible mechanism that is not mentioned, and that is that the excavation is formed by the fibers of the optic nerve retracting, because they are also pulled by the tissues that make up the central nervous system.

Keywords: CSF, Glaucoma, intraocular pressure, optic disc, water dissociation, brain ventricles.

Introduction

Glaucoma is the second leading cause of permanent blindness in the United States and occurs most often in older adults [5]. Glaucoma is defined as an acquired loss of retinal ganglion cells and axons within the optic nerve or optic neuropathy that results in a characteristic optic nerve head appearance and a corresponding progressive loss of vision (Figure 1). The patient with POAG is often asymptomatic until the optic

nerve damage is severe unless signs of early glaucoma are recognized on a routine eye exam. normal or low-tension type glaucoma in which patients have the same visual loss pattern as POAG but at normal intraocular pressure readings. Currently, glaucoma cannot be prevented or cured, but progression can be controlled to help prevent further vision loss either through medication, glaucoma laser treatment, or incisional glaucoma surgeries.

⁵ Dietze J, Blair K, Havens SJ. Glaucoma. 2022 Jun 27. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2023 Jan-. PMID: 30855805.

Figure 1. Example of Glaucomatous optic nerve excavation. The characteristic aspect of the optic nerve for primary open angle glaucoma is usually bilateral. (Left image: right eye, right image, left eye). At the bottom of the excavation, part of the cribriform plate of the sclera can be seen.

In the normal optic nerve (figure 2), there may be a very small excavation in the center of the optic nerve.

Figure 2.

Normal appearance of the optic nerve. On the left, the patient's right eye. On the right, the patient's left eye.

In glaucoma or glaucomatous optic neuropathy, the excavation tends to extend and deepen. (Figure 3)

Figure 3. Right eye (left), left eye (right), of a patient with primary advanced open angle glaucoma.

The mechanism that is assumed to produce the pathological increase in the excavation of the optic nerve, and for almost 150 years, is the increase in intraocular pressure (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Why increased intraocular pressure markedly affects the anatomy of the optic nerve is not understood, and as in other areas of medicine, also poor understood, the explanation is based on mathematical models.

To date, it has always been pointed out that the cause of said progressive excavation of the optic nerve is the push on said anatomical structure because of the increase in intraocular pressure.

But until now it has not been postulated that increased cupping of the optic nerve results more from exquisite traction on the optic nerve tissue than from the push of intraocular pressure.

So far, it has not been adequately examined whether the excavation of the optic nerve (Figure 5) is a result of it being pushed (due to elevated intraocular pressure) or it is being pulled by intracranial tissues, and in a delicate way because the diameter of the optic nerve is equivalent to twelve hairs, humans, together.

Figure 5. So, the optic nerve is pushed back by the increased IOP? Or is it pulled back because the intracranial nervous tissue and its components are retracting?

Neurodegeneration in glaucoma extends beyond the eye into the lateral geniculate nucleus and visual cortex, and the disease even shares some characteristics

with other central nervous system degenerative disorders. Glaucoma destroys neurons through oxidative stress, impairment in axonal transport, neuroinflammation, and excitotoxicity [6].

⁶ Gauthier AC, Liu J. Neurodegeneration and Neuroprotection in Glaucoma. *Yale J Biol Med.* 2016 Mar 24;89(1):73-9. PMID: 27505018; PMCID: PMC4797839.

Recent research has linked POAG to degeneration of the central nervous system (CNS). Glaucoma-associated neurodegeneration has been noted in the intracranial optic nerves, lateral geniculate nucleus (LGN), and visual cortex of primates and humans [7].

One case study compared the brain of a glaucoma patient with a superior visual field defect to three brains of age-matched controls without neurological or ocular disease [8]. Tissue samples from the lateral geniculate nucleus (LGN) at autopsy showed shrunken neurons with smaller nuclei and more globoid cytoplasm in both the magnocellular and parvocellular layers in the glaucoma patient compared to the controls. In addition, cortical ribbon thickness under the calcarine sulcus was diminished, and optic nerve tissue was heavily atrophied.

Previous study demonstrated decreased cell density in the magnocellular layer in glaucoma patients compared to healthy controls [9]. These studies indicate that the effects of glaucoma can extend beyond the eye into areas that process visual information within the brain. Although there is also the possibility that the degeneration of the nerve fibers began in the LGN and then spread to the orbital and intrascleral portion of the optic nerve, which would result in a glaucomatous excavation, but because the nerve fibers are being pulled from the CNS, and not so much due to some or any increase in intraocular pressure, for example in the case of normal tension glaucoma.

And if this is the case, it explains why intensive hypotensive treatments and even heroic surgeries that seek to lower intraocular pressure beyond 7 mm Hg do not give results and are even complicated quite frequently with macular edema or sometimes with hemorrhages in vitreous body, given the very low intraocular tension.

Therefore, we must consider that the characteristic appearance of the optic disc in the case of glaucoma may be due to the increase in intraocular pressure, with the consequent atrophy (by pressure) of the retinal ganglion cell layer, which is where the axons that make up the optic nerve or tract, are originated. Thereafter, these neuron fibers go to the CNS through the optic foramen, intersects approximately 60/40% in the optic chiasm, and makes the first synapse of the visual pathway in the thalamus, the great sensory receptor and, specifically in the lateral geniculate nucleus.

So we are talking about a Wallerian degeneration that can begin in various places along the visual pathway, both in the eye, locally; and/or some location of the CNS, including in the occipital region, in the region

of the calcarine fissure region, given that the degeneration of neurons can be even of trans-neuronal type, which would explain the failure of anti-glaucomatous treatments in a significant number of cases.

Lesions of the visual pathway, located intracranially, are not isolated but are usually part of a pathology that covers areas or regions, so the main symptoms are neurological. And neurological problems that cause an increase in the volume of the ventricles, and therefore retraction of the nervous tissue, have a greater possibility of developing glaucomatous changes in the optic nerve, but not because of the push of intraocular pressure, but because the nerve fibers of the optic tract are being pulled from inside the skull.

In some diseases, the relationship between the enlargement of the ventricles volume and the association con normal tension glaucoma (NTG) has been described. For instance, in Alzheimer's Disease [10],

Primary open-angle glaucoma (POAG) is an optic neuropathy characterized by progressive degeneration of the optic nerve that leads to irreversible visual impairment. Multiple epidemiological studies suggest an association between POAG and major neurodegenerative disorders (Alzheimer's disease, amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, frontotemporal dementia, and Parkinson's disease) [11]. The results of this study shed light on the neurodegenerative process of POAG linked to brain morphology by identifying several regions of the brain that causally affect the risk of POAG. This study also identified shared biological mechanisms. These findings indicate that brain morphology in several regions causally influences the neurodegenerative process of POAG, and highlighting regions of the brain that could potentially serve as neuroimaging biomarkers of glaucoma.

The nature of the overlap between neurodegenerative disorders and glaucoma remains controversial, however, as a neurodegenerative condition, POAG has been linked through MRI to the decrease of white matter and the visual cortex density [12], as well as the reduction of cortical thickness in the frontal pole and amygdala in observational studies [13].

Thereby, there is a distinctive and causal neurodegenerative process in glaucoma that involves morphological brain changes that lead to the decrease of retinal ganglion cells and retinal nerve fibers.

A possible shared biological mechanism between neurodegenerative diseases that is likely linked to the vascular and inflammatory processes of glaucoma

⁷ Yucel YH, Zhang Q, Weinreb RN, Kaufman PL, Gupta N. Effects of retinal ganglion cell loss on magno-, parvo-, koniocellular pathways in the lateral geniculate nucleus and visual cortex in glaucoma. *Prog Retin Eye Res.* 2003;22(4):465–481.

⁸ Gupta N, Ang L, de Tilly LN, Bidaisee L, Yucel YH. Human glaucoma and neural degeneration in intracranial optic nerve, lateral geniculate nucleus, and visual cortex. *Br J Ophthalmol.* 2006;90(6):674–678.

⁹ Chaturvedi N, Hedley-Whyte ET, Dreyer EB. Lateral geniculate nucleus in glaucoma. *Am J Ophthalmol.* 1993;116(2):182–188.

¹⁰ Ekström C, Puhto I, Kilander L. Association between open-angle glaucoma and Alzheimer's disease in Sweden: a long-term population-based follow-up study. *Ups J Med Sci.* 2021 Jun 21;126. doi: 10.48101/ujms.v126.7819. PMID: 34349887; PMCID: PMC8276346.

¹¹ Diaz-Torres S, He W, Thorp J, Seddighi S, Mullany S; IGGC International Glaucoma Genetics Consortium; Hammond CJ, Hysi PG, Pasquale LR, Khawaja AP, Hewitt AW, Craig JE, Mackey DA, Wiggs JL, van Duijn C, Lupton MK, Ong JS, MacGregor S, Gharahkhani P. Disentangling the genetic overlap and causal relationships between primary open-angle glaucoma, brain morphology and four major neurodegenerative disorders. *EBioMedicine.* 2023 Jun;92:104615. doi: 10.1016/j.ebiom.2023.104615. Epub 2023 May 16. PMID: 37201334; PMCID: PMC10206164.

¹² Fiedorowicz M, Dyda W, Rejdak R, Grieb P. Magnetic resonance in studies of glaucoma. *Med Sci Monit.* 2011;17(10):RA227–RA232. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.12659/msm.881973>.

¹³ Wang J, Li T, Sabel BA, et al. Structural brain alterations in primary open angle glaucoma: a 3T MRI study. *Sci Rep.* 2016;6:18969. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep18969>.

could be related to our finding about that source of oxygen of human body is not the atmosphere, instead is the intracellular water, like in plants [14].

Retraction of nervous tissue is a common finding in neurodegenerative diseases [15]. It is explained by the progressive loss of neurons, neuron structure, and/or their functions, known as neurodegeneration, and it is central to the pathophysiology of several brain disorders [16]. Neurodegeneration is associated with dysfunction of the synapse, neural network, and the deposition of physiochemically altered variants of proteins in the brain [17]. The most common neurodegenerative diseases (NDs) include Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease, prion disease, Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, motor neuron disease, Huntington's disease, spinal muscular atrophy, and spinocerebellar ataxia [18].

And NDs characteristically present with an increase in the volume of the ventricles and the subarachnoid space, which until now is explained by the retraction of the nervous tissue that usually reaches the optic nerve, pulling it backwards, which produces an ophthalmoscopic picture very similar to primary glaucoma of open angle, probably due to elevated intraocular pressure.

The increase in the volume of the ventricles has been explained until now as a rather passive phenomenon, in which the retracted neural tissue leaves more space, which is filled naturally and passively with cerebrospinal fluid. (Figures 6, 7)

Figure 6. Ventricular dilation is a frequent finding in NDS, which is not given much attention because it is thought to be secondary to atrophy and/or degeneration of the nervous tissue, and on the other hand, the evaluation of the volume of the ventricles is not it's simple.

¹⁴ : Arturo Solís Herrera, María del Carmen Arias Esparza (2022) Oxygen from the Atmosphere Cannot Pass Through the Lung Tissues and Reach the Bloodstream. The Unexpected Capacity of Human Body to Dissociate the Water Molecule. Journal of Pulmonology Research & Reports. SRC/JPRR-133. DOI: doi.org/10.47363/JPRR/2022(4)124

¹⁵ Lamprey, R.N.L.; Chaulagain, B.; Trivedi, R.; Gothwal, A.; Layek, B.; Singh, J. A Review of the Common Neurodegenerative Disorders: Current Therapeutic Approaches and the Potential Role of Nanotherapeutics. Int. J. Mol. Sci. 2022, 23, 1851. https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms23031851

¹⁶ Przedborski, S.; Vila, M.; Jackson-Lewis, V. Series Introduction: Neurodegeneration: What is it and where are we? J. Clin. Investig. 2003, 111, 3–10.

¹⁷ Hoover, B.R.; Reed, M.N.; Su, J.; Penrod, R.D.; Kotilinek, L.A.; Grant, M.K.; Pitsstick, R.; Carlson, G.A.; Lanier, L.M.; Yuan, L.-L. Tau mislocalization to dendritic spines mediates synaptic dysfunction independently of neurodegeneration. Neuron 2010, 68, 1067–1081.

¹⁸ Hague, S.; Klaffke, S.; Bandmann, O. Neurodegenerative disorders: Parkinson's disease and Huntington's disease. J. Neurol. Neurosurg. Psychiatry 2005, 76, 1058–1063.

Figure 7. In this case of Kuru, the dilation of the ventricles and the subarachnoid space is evident, but in light of our discovery about the various molecules present in the CNS, and throughout the organism, capable of dissociating water, like plants ; then it is possible that the water in the cerebrospinal fluid accumulates because it is not dissociating properly, which could constitute the initial problem, since the dissociation of water is compromised, and it is the fundamental chemical reaction of life, then degeneration or atrophy occurs of the nervous tissue and it is consequent to the poor dissociation of water. Let us remember that in any system, when energy decreases, mass tends to disappear.

So, if we maintain the dissociation of water, which constitutes the initial reaction of life, the tissues tend to recover in a surprising way, as illustrated by the following photographs, of a case of traumatic hyphema, in a 25-year-old male patient. which was disposed of in the hospitals of the government health system.

Figure 8. Male patient in his third decade of life, who was struck by a burr thrown at high speed by a lawnmower. The upper left photograph, taken with diffuse light, allows us to appreciate the characteristic folds of severe corneal edema. The rest of the photographs show a significant amount of blood in the anterior chamber. These photographs were taken three days after the trauma.

Figure 9. Photographs taken with different wavelengths, showing an intense ciliary reaction.

Figure 10. The treatment was based on maintaining the dissociation of water pharmacologically, through the administration of QIAPI 1™, at a dose of three drops every hour. As the days went by, the blood began to dissolve and be reabsorbed, being able to prevent hematic impregnation of the cornea. The iris is seen covered with a layer of fibrin.

Figure 11. The photograph, taken 11 days after the initial examination, shows an already small blood level, and the corneal edema in clear improvement.

Figure 12. These photographs, taken with different wavelengths, show faint blood remains on the whitish layer that covers the surface of the iris.

Figure 13. This photograph taken 22 days after the initial examination, already shows that the blood has mostly disappeared, leaving faint blood remains covering the fibrin layer. The cornea appears clear, with minimal edema.

Figure 14.

Photographs taken with different wavelengths show a transparent cornea with increasingly less blood remains.

Figure 15. 4 months later, areas can be seen where the iris has disappeared, the whitish membrane that covered the surface of the iris has decreased considerably and allows the specular reflection of the back of the eye to be captured.

Figure 16. The fundus image, 4 months after the initial examination, is surprisingly preserved, despite the severe trauma that induced the hyphema. And curiously, despite having had high intraocular pressure, sometimes more than 40 mm Hg, the papilla is not excavated.

Figure 17. The fundus images, taken with different wavelengths, show a surprising anatomical integrity, given the background, and the optic disc is not excavated, which calls into question that the increase in intraocular pressure pushes the head back. of the optic nerve.

Figure 18. The anatomical integrity of the anterior segment is remarkable and allows us to predict a good prognosis in terms of vision. The patient was managed all this time with QIAPI 1™, every hour. To date, no surgery has been performed.

Conclusions

At least in two clinical studies investigating the prevalence of primary open-angle glaucoma (POAG) in patients with AD, the results show an increased occurrence of POAG in patients with AD [19]. 50 % of the patients in the first study had normal tension glaucoma (NTG), and almost all in the second study [20].

Since 1980, it was proposed that Age-related macular degeneration is the equivalent of the Alzheimer's Disease of the eye [21], and in 2003 some experimental results support the view of glaucoma as an ocular AD [22]. Thereby, the cellular mechanism underlying neuronal degeneration in glaucoma has parallels with Alzheimer's disease [23].

However, the results in clinical trials have been conflicting since the treatments used in AD do not work in POAG or LPG nor in ARMD [24] and vice versa. But the parallels observed support the idea that with treatment alone we can improve the three diseases mentioned [25]. And if clinical trials have failed to date, it is probably because the etiopathogenesis of these diseases has not been adequately understood.

In the case of hyphema that we present, the administration of a medication (QIAPI 1™), which maintains the dissociation of water inside the cell at adequate levels, allowing the levels of oxygen, hydrogen, and high-energy electrons to be conserved at optimal levels, it allows a surprising recovery of the tissues, as well as protecting the optic nerve from excavation due to high intraocular pressure.

The results of our research point to the fact that we must rethink the biology of both the central nervous system [26] and the human eye [27].

Acknowledgements: This work was supported by an unrestricted grant from Human Photosynthesis™ Research Center, Aguascalientes 20000, México.

Public disclaimer: The finding of the unsuspected capacity of several molecules presents in eukaryotic cell, capable of dissociating the water molecule, as the development of QIAPI 1™, was done at our facilities in Aguascalientes, México.

All authors contributed to the writing of the article.

References

1. Dietze J, Blair K, Havens SJ. Glaucoma. 2022 Jun 27. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2023 Jan–. PMID: 30855805.
2. Gauthier AC, Liu J. Neurodegeneration and Neuroprotection in Glaucoma. *Yale J Biol Med*. 2016

Mar 24;89(1):73-9. PMID: 27505018; PMCID: PMC4797839.

3. Yucel YH, Zhang Q, Weinreb RN, Kaufman PL, Gupta N. Effects of retinal ganglion cell loss on magno-, parvo-, koniocellular pathways in the lateral geniculate nucleus and visual cortex in glaucoma. *Prog Retin Eye Res*. 2003;22(4):465–481.

4. Gupta N, Ang L, de Tilly LN, Bidaisee L, Yücel YH. Human glaucoma and neural degeneration in intracranial optic nerve, lateral geniculate nucleus, and visual cortex. *Br J Ophthalmol*. 2006;90(6):674–678.

5. Chaturvedi N, Hedley-Whyte ET, Dreyer EB. Lateral geniculate nucleus in glaucoma. *Am J Ophthalmol*. 1993;116(2):182–188.

6. Ekström C, Puhto I, Kilander L. Association between open-angle glaucoma and Alzheimer's disease in Sweden: a long-term population-based follow-up study. *Ups J Med Sci*. 2021 Jun 21;126. doi: 10.48101/ujms.v126.7819. PMID: 34349887; PMCID: PMC8276346.

7. Diaz-Torres S, He W, Thorp J, Seddighi S, Mullany S; IGGC International Glaucoma Genetics Consortium; Hammond CJ, Hysi PG, Pasquale LR, Khawaja AP, Hewitt AW, Craig JE, Mackey DA, Wiggs JL, van Duijn C, Lupton MK, Ong JS, MacGregor S, Gharahkhani P. Disentangling the genetic overlap and causal relationships between primary open-angle glaucoma, brain morphology and four major neurodegenerative disorders. *EBioMedicine*. 2023 Jun;92:104615. doi: 10.1016/j.ebiom.2023.104615. Epub 2023 May 16. PMID: 37201334; PMCID: PMC10206164.

8. Fiedorowicz M, Dyda W, Rejdak R, Grieb P. Magnetic resonance in studies of glaucoma. *Med Sci Monit*. 2011;17(10):RA227–RA232. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.12659/msm.881973>.

9. Wang J, Li T, Sabel BA, et al. Structural brain alterations in primary open angle glaucoma: a 3T MRI study. *Sci Rep*. 2016;6:18969. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep18969>.

10. : Arturo Solís Herrera, María del Carmen Arias Esparza (2022) Oxygen from the Atmosphere Cannot Pass Through the Lung Tissues and Reach the Bloodstream. The Unexpected Capacity of Human Body to Dissociate the Water Molecule. *Journal of Pulmonology Research & Reports*. SRC/JPRR-133. DOI: [doi.org/10.47363/JPRR/2022\(4\)124](https://doi.org/10.47363/JPRR/2022(4)124)

11. Lamptey, R.N.L.; Chaulagain, B.; Trivedi, R.; Gothwal, A.; Layek, B.; Singh, J. A Review of the

¹⁹ Bayer AU, Keller ON, Ferrari F & Maag KP (2002): Association of glaucoma with neurodegenerative diseases with apoptotic cell death: Alzheimer's disease and Parkinson's disease. *Am J Ophthalmol* **133**: 135–137.

²⁰ Tamura H, Kawakami H, Kanamoto T et al. (2006): High frequency of open-angle glaucoma in Japanese patients with Alzheimer's disease. *J Neurol Sci* **246**: 79–83.

²¹ Kaarniranta K, Salminen A, Haapasalo A, Soininen H, Hiltunen M. Age-related macular degeneration (AMD): Alzheimer's disease in the eye? *J Alzheimers Dis*. 2011;24(4):615–31. doi: 10.3233/JAD-2011-101908. PMID: 21297256.

²² McKinnon SJ (2003): Glaucoma: ocular Alzheimer's disease? *Front Biosci* **8**: s1140–s1156.

²³ Vickers JC (1997): The cellular mechanism underlying neuronal degeneration in glaucoma: parallels with Alzheimer's disease. *Aust N Z J Ophthalmol* **25**: 105–109.

²⁴ Krupin T (2007): A clinical trial studying neuroprotection in low-pressure glaucoma. *Eye* **21**: S51–S54.

²⁵ Osborne NN (2009): Recent clinical findings with memantine should not mean that the idea of neuroprotection in glaucoma is abandoned. *Acta Ophthalmol* **87**: 450–454.

²⁶ Arturo Solís Herrera, et al. "The Relationship between Low Tension Glaucoma, CSF, the Size of the Ventricles, and Neurodegenerative Diseases". *EC Neurology* **12.8** (2020): 183-222

²⁷ Herrera AS, Del C A Esparza M, Md Ashraf G, Zamyatnin AA, Aliev G. Beyond mitochondria, what would be the energy source of the cell? *Cent Nerv Syst Agents Med Chem*. 2015;15(1):32-41. doi: 10.2174/1871524915666150203093656. PMID: 25645910.

Common Neurodegenerative Disorders: Current Therapeutic Approaches and the Potential Role of Nanotherapeutics. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 2022, 23, 1851. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms23031851>

12. Przedborski, S.; Vila, M.; Jackson-Lewis, V. Series Introduction: Neurodegeneration: What is it and where are we? *J. Clin. Investig.* 2003, 111, 3–10.

13. Hoover, B.R.; Reed, M.N.; Su, J.; Penrod, R.D.; Kotilinek, L.A.; Grant, M.K.; Pitsstick, R.; Carlson, G.A.; Lanier, L.M.; Yuan, L.-L. Tau mislocalization to dendritic spines mediates synaptic dysfunction independently of neurodegeneration. *Neuron* 2010, 68, 1067–1081.

14. Hague, S.; Klaffke, S.; Bandmann, O. Neurodegenerative disorders: Parkinson's disease and Huntington's disease. *J. Neurol. Neurosurg. Psychiatry* 2005, 76, 1058–1063.

15. Bayer AU, Keller ON, Ferrari F & Maag KP (2002): Association of glaucoma with neurodegenerative diseases with apoptotic cell death: Alzheimer's disease and Parkinson's disease. *Am J Ophthalmol* 133: 135–137.

16. Tamura H, Kawakami H, Kanamoto T et al. (2006): High frequency of open-angle glaucoma in Japanese patients with Alzheimer's disease. *J Neurol Sci* 246: 79–83.

17. Kaarniranta K, Salminen A, Haapasalo A, Soininen H, Hiltunen M. Age-related macular degeneration (AMD): Alzheimer's disease in the eye? *J Alzheimers Dis.* 2011;24(4):615-31. doi: 10.3233/JAD-2011-101908. PMID: 21297256.

18. McKinnon SJ (2003): Glaucoma: ocular Alzheimer's disease? *Front Biosci* 8: s1140–s1156.

19. Vickers JC (1997): The cellular mechanism underlying neuronal degeneration in glaucoma: parallels with Alzheimer's disease. *Aust N Z J Ophthalmol* 25: 105–109.

20. Krupin T (2007): A clinical trial studying neuroprotection in low-pressure glaucoma. *Eye* 21: S51–S54.

21. Osborne NN (2009): Recent clinical findings with memantine should not mean that the idea of neuroprotection in glaucoma is abandoned. *Acta Ophthalmol* 87: 450–454.

22. Arturo Solís Herrera., et al. "The Relationship between Low Tension Glaucoma, CSF, the Size of the Ventricles, and Neurodegenerative Diseases". *EC Neurology* 12.8 (2020): 183-222

23. Herrera AS, Del C A Esparza M, Md Ashraf G, Zamyatnin AA, Aliev G. Beyond mitochondria, what would be the energy source of the cell? *Cent Nerv Syst Agents Med Chem.* 2015;15(1):32-41. doi: 10.2174/1871524915666150203093656. PMID: 25645910.